

ABOUT ROLE OF BRITTLE LAYERS IN FIBRE COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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The influence of brittle layers on the ultimate tensile strength of metal matrix composites is discussed. An equation has been derived to calculate the first critical thickness of the layer. It has been shown existence of two types of the influence of fracture of the layer on fracture of the fibre. Criterion of the existence of one of them is value of local stress in fibre's material near tip of crack, which situates at the fibre-layer interface. Experimental results fitted theoretical ones well. On the base of the theory it has been developed the theoretical method for calculation of the critical stress intensity factor K_{I0} for the brittle fibres.

Introduction

Nowdays there is an increasing interest in the problem of the influence of the interface layer on tensile strength of metal fibre composites. The problem has great practical significance because increasingly composites are developed which have either protective deposits on the fibres or an interaction zone between matrix and fibres. The majority of experimental results shows that the tensile strength of composites decreases if the thickness of the layers increases. Present paper develops the latter approach in a more general sense.

The critical thickness of the brittle interface layer

Let us consider a simple model system as shown in Fig.I, which represents a fibre and concentric interface layer. The interface behaviour of the fibre and the layer has a strength of not less than the component of the model and is considered to ideally smooth. The diameter of the fibre d_f is constant and the fibres are of unit length. Stress is applied along the axis of the fibre and parallel of it.

Fig. I. The model system - fibre/layer

Weibull has shown (I) that the strength of brittle materials is affected by their volume according to the equation

$$\sigma_1/\sigma_2 = \left(V_2/V_1 \right)^{1/\beta} \quad (1)$$

where σ_1 and σ_2 are the average tensile strength of the brittle material, which has volumes V_1 and V_2 accordingly; β is a Weibull coefficient, it shows the strength distribution of the material. Experimental data have shown that the tensile strength of brittle layer is increased by a decrease in their thickness. It is possible to transform equation (I) into the form

$$\bar{\sigma}_{l1}/\bar{\sigma}_{l2} = \left(F_{l2}/F_{l1} \right)^{1/\beta_l} \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_{l1}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{l2}$ are average tensile strength of brittle layers which have respectively cross section areas F_{l1} and F_{l2} ; β_l is a Weibull coefficient of the tensile strength distribution of the layer.

If the layer thickness changes there are three different cases. In the first the failure strain of the layer ϵ_{ul} is less than that of the fibre ϵ_{uf} , which is considered as constant in this model. The layer fractures first and is followed by fracture of the fibre. In the second case ϵ_{ul} is greater than ϵ_{uf} , therefore the fibre fractures first and is followed by the fracture of the layer. Thirdly ϵ_{ul} equals ϵ_{uf} . Here fracture of its components occurs simultaneously, i.e.

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{uf} = \bar{\epsilon}_{ul} \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{\epsilon}_{uf}$ and $\bar{\epsilon}_{ul}$ are average failure strains of the fibre and the layer respectively. Equation (3) is transformed into the following

$$\bar{\sigma}_{uf}/E_f = \bar{\sigma}_{ul}/E_l \quad (4)$$

where E_f and E_l are Young moduli of the fibre and the layer respectively; $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}$ is the average tensile strength of the fibre; $\bar{\sigma}_{ul}$ is the average tensile strength of a layer of given thickness. We shall call it critical thickness for the present. If

we assume $\sigma_{ul} = \sigma_{l1}$, $F_L = F_{L1}$, $F_L^* = F_{L2}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{ul} = \bar{\sigma}_{l2}$ then equations (2) and (4) will give us the following equation

$$F_L^* = F_L \left(\frac{E_f \bar{\sigma}_{ul}}{E_L \bar{\sigma}_{uf}} \right)^{\beta_L} \quad (5)$$

where F_L^* is the critical cross sectional area of the layer of critical thickness. It is more convenient to use another equation which is a modification of equation 5. This equation has the following form

$$t^* = \left[\left(\frac{d_f}{2} \right)^2 + t (d_f + t_l) \left(\frac{E_f \bar{\sigma}_{ul}}{E_L \bar{\sigma}_{uf}} \right)^{\beta_L} \right]^{1/2} - \frac{d_f}{2} \quad (6)$$

where t_l is the known value of the thickness of the layer of which $\bar{\sigma}_{ul}$ is known, t_l^* is the critical thickness of the layer, d_f is the diameter of the fibre. It will be possible to simplify equation (6), if we put $\bar{\sigma}_{ul}^n$ in place of $\bar{\sigma}_{ul}$. Here $\bar{\sigma}_{ul}^n$ is the normalized value of the strength of the layer. The latter corresponds to the cross sectional area of the layer, which equals to the cross sectional area of the fibre. So, we have

$$t_l^* = \frac{d_f}{2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{E_f \bar{\sigma}_{ul}^n}{E_L \bar{\sigma}_{uf}} \right)^{\beta_L}} - 1 \right] \quad (7)$$

$\bar{\sigma}_{ul}^n$ can be calculated from equation (2). Equation (7) shows, that t_l^* increases with the diameter of the fibre, and the ratio $E_f \bar{\sigma}_{ul}^n / E_L \bar{\sigma}_{uf}$. In the latter case t_l^* increases in parabolic fashion (Fig.2). If $E_f \bar{\sigma}_{ul}^n / E_L \bar{\sigma}_{uf} = 1$ then $t_l^* \approx 0,2 d_f$. Therefore from a practical point of view it is desirable to select materials for fibres and protective layers in such a way that the ratio $E_f \bar{\sigma}_{ul}^n / E_L \bar{\sigma}_{uf}$ will be as high as possible. If the ratio is less than a unit, then t_l^* will decrease with increasing β_L and vice versa (Fig.2).

Now we have an equation which enables us to calculate the critical thickness of the brittle interface layer for any composite material containing brittle fibres. If $t_l < t_l^*$, then the layer will break first and only after that will the fibre break. Cracks which appear as a result of the fracture of the layer affect the fracture resistance of the fibre. They are in fact notches in the fibre. In the next section of our paper we shall show the interaction between these cracks and the fibre.

Fig. 2. The graph which shows how t_l^* is affected by $\frac{E_f \bar{\sigma}_l^n}{E_l \bar{\sigma}_f}$

The influence of cracks in the layer on fibre fracture

Ustinov et al. (2) has studied the microstructure peculiarities of fractured layers in aluminium/steel composite. Their experimental data have enabled them to construct a model of the propagation of cracks throughout the layer. According to this model (Fig.3) the cracks appear at the layer/matrix in-

Fig. 3. The model of crack propagation in the fibre/layer system.

terface (point S). The crack propagates through the layer towards the layer/fibre interface. Eventually the crack reaches the fibre at the layer/fibre interface (point C). If stress intensity at point C is not enough to cause fracture of the fibre then the crack will by-pass the fibre completely. Otherwise the crack will enter the fibre and will propagate through the layer and the fibre simultaneously (Fig.3). So in fact we have to discuss two different types of fracture. The first type (point C) is analogous to the fracture of a semi-infinite plate with an edge crack. The second type is analogous to the fracture of a bar with a circular crack.

Let us discuss the first case. It is represented by the model in Fig.4. The model consists of a semi-infinite plate of two different brittle materials. They are separated by the interface, which is parallel to the edge of the plate. The interface is strong enough to resist delamination. One component of the model, i.e. the layer, has only one finite dimension apart from thickness of course. It is equal to the thickness of the layer. This component contains the crack with its tip at the interface. At infinity there are applied stresses which are parallel to the interface. They have different values which are proportional to Young moduli of these components. This is a state of plane strain. Experimental data which have been obtained by Ustinov et al (2) permit us to regard the crack as quasi-static.

If the model system is homogeneous, i.e. in fact the two components have similar properties, then the stress around point C (Fig.4) will be given by the equations

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{xx} &= \frac{K_I}{(2\pi r)^{1/2}} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \left[1 - \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \sin \frac{3\theta}{2} \right] \\ \sigma_{yy} &= \frac{K_I}{(2\pi r)^{1/2}} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \left[1 + \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \sin \frac{3\theta}{2} \right] \\ \tau_{xy} &= \frac{K_I}{(2\pi r)^{1/2}} \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \cos \frac{3\theta}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where r is the distance from the tip of the crack (point C) to a certain point, θ is the angle between X axis and radius-vector r . We are more interested in stress σ_{yy} at a distance from point C of not more than approximately one atomic radius $r = r^*$. So if $\theta = 0$ then equations (8) become the following

$$\sigma_{yy} = \frac{K_I}{(2\pi r^*)^{1/2}} \quad (9)$$

where K_I is the stress intensity factor. Paris and Sih (3) have shown that in case of a single phase model system K_I is described by the equation

$$K_I = 1,12 \sigma (\pi \alpha)^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

where σ is the nominal stress, α is the greater semiaxis of the elliptical crack. If we come back to our model system which consists of two different materials, we must assume that K_I will be affected by the difference between the properties of these materials (4,5). So we shall introduce the special factor α_1 , which is affected by the ratio E_1/E_f . So that we have

$$K_I = 1,12 \alpha_1 \sigma (\pi \alpha)^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

If we insert in equations (9) and (11) σ_f , t_1 instead of σ , α respectively we obtain the following equation

$$\sigma_{yy} = 0,79 \alpha_1 \sigma_f \left(\frac{t}{r^*}\right)^{1/2} \quad (12)$$

where σ_f is the tensile stress in the fibre. We assume that $\sigma_f = \sigma_{uf}$, where σ_{uf} is the fracture stress of the fibre. Here the fracture of the fibre, which is initiated by the crack in the layer, occurs in practice simultaneously with the fracture of the layer, i.e. at the fracture strain of the layer $\bar{\epsilon}_{ul}$. Therefore σ_{uf} is defined by equations (2) and (3) in the following way

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{uf}}{E_f} = \bar{\epsilon}_{uf} = \bar{\epsilon}_{ul} = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{ul}}{E_l} = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{l1}}{E_l} = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{l2}}{E_l} \left(\frac{F_{l2}}{F_{l1}}\right)^{1/\beta_l}$$

and finally

$$\bar{\sigma}_{uf} = \frac{E_f}{E_l} \bar{\sigma}_{l2} \left(\frac{t_{l2}}{t_{l1}}\right)^{1/\beta_l} \quad (13)$$

After substituting t_{l1} , t_{l2} , $\bar{\sigma}_{l2}$ by t'_l , t_l , σ_{ul} respectively and inserting equation (13) into equation (12), we have the general equation

$$\sigma_{yy}^I = 0,79 \alpha_1 \frac{E_f}{E_l} \bar{\sigma}_{ul} t_l^{1/\beta_l} (r^*)^{-1/2} (t_l')^{1/2 - 1/\beta_l} \quad (I4)$$

Here $\bar{\sigma}_{ul}$ and t_l are the known values of the strength and thickness of the layer respectively, t_l' is the current values of the thickness of the layer. Equation I4 shows that σ_{yy}^I increases with t_l' (Fig.5). If σ_{yy}^I is greater than $\sigma_{uf}^t \cong E_f/10$ (σ_{uf}^t is the theoretical ultimate tensile strength of the fibre material), then the fracture of the layer will immediately initiate the fracture of the fibre at point C (Fig.4).

Let us calculate σ_{yy}^I for a number of well-known layer/fibre systems at condition $t_l^* = t_l'$ and conclude will the fracture of the layer immediately initiate the fracture of the fibre or will it not. At first we should calculate the critical thickness of the layer t_l^* by equation (7) and after that σ_{yy}^I by equation (I4). Results of the calculation are shown in Table I. The layer and the fibre will fracture simultaneously if $\sigma_{yy}^I > \sigma_{uf}^t$. Kelly (6) has shown that the factor β_l equals from 3 to 6. Table I shows that for system B/(BN) where the ratio $E_f \bar{\sigma}_{ul}^n / \bar{\sigma}_{uf} E_l \gg 1$ in practice there is no harmful effect of the layer of any thickness on the strength of the fibres. For three systems B/(B₄C), B/(SiC) and B/(BN) the fracture of the layer of the critical thickness in practice always initiates

Fig. 4. The first model of the fracture of the fibre/layer system.

Table I. The calculated characteristics of number systems fibre/layer

Fibre/ layer (depo- sit)	Fibre		Layer (deposit) t_l^*				Fac- tors α_1 and α_2	σ_{uf}^t kg/mm ²	Stress σ_{yy}^I kg/mm ²	Will the fibre fracture due to σ_{yy}^I	Stress σ_{yy}^{II} kg/mm ²	Will the fibre fracture due to σ_{yy}^{II}
	$E_f \times 10^{-3}$ kg/mm ²	$\bar{\sigma}_{uf,2}$ kg/mm ²	$E_l \times 10^{-3}$ kg/mm ²	$\bar{\sigma}_{ul,2}^n$ kg/mm ²	β_l	μ						
B/(SiC)	38	350	47	230	3	3,62	>I	3800	28528 α_1	yes	-	-
"	"	"	"	"	4	1,90	"	"	21058 α_1	"	-	-
"	"	"	"	"	5	1,04	"	"	15624 α_1	"	-	-
"	"	"	"	"	6	0,51	"	"	11164 α_1	"	-	-
B/(B ₄ C)	"	"	"	"	3	3,62	"	"	28528 α_1	"	-	-
"	"	"	"	"	4	1,90	"	"	21058 α_1	"	-	-
"	"	"	"	"	5	1,04	"	"	15624 α_1	"	-	-
"	"	"	"	"	6	0,51	"	"	11164 α_1	"	-	-
B/(BN)	"	"	9	140	3	70,6	<I	"	148787 α_1	"	-	-
"	"	"	"	"	4	101,13	"	"	180814 α_1	"	-	-
"	"	"	"	"	5	141,97	"	"	217079 α_1	"	-	-
"	"	"	"	"	6	196,0	"	"	258034 α_1	"	-	-
B/TiB ₂	"	"	51	100	3	0,24	>I	"	7270 α_1	"	-	-
"	"	"	"	"	4	0,05	"	"	3397 α_1	?	27222 α_2	yes
"	"	"	"	"	5	0,011	"	"	1599 α_1	no	27300 α_2	yes
"	"	"	"	"	6	0,002	"	"	705 α_1	no	28239 α_2	yes
B/AlB ₂	"	"	42	70	3	0,145	"	"	5679 α_1	yes	-	-
"	"	"	"	"	4	0,030	"	"	2540 α_1	?	26285 α_2	yes
"	"	"	"	"	5	0,005	"	"	1072 α_1	no	27167 α_2	yes
"	"	"	"	"	6	0,0008	"	"	441 α_1	no	27964 α_2	yes

immediate fracture of the fibre. Morin (7) has shown for the system B/(B₄C) that the strength of the fibre begins to decrease when the thickness of the layer will be more than 7-8 μ. This more or less coincides with the calculated value of the critical thickness of the layer of B₄C when β_l equals 3-4. Camahort (8) and Ryder et al. (9) have shown that the tensile strength of system B/(BN) did not decrease when the thickness of the layer was equal to ~ 0,4 μ. Unfortunately there is no more data about this system. Nevertheless the existing data does not contradict our calculated values for this system.

There are systems (in table I there are two of them - B/TiB₂ and B/AlB₂), where the fracture of the layer does not always initiate immediately fracture of the fibre. In this case it means that the crack in the layer at the moment of meeting with the fibre at point C (Fig.3) creates σ_{yy}^I, which is less than σ_{uf}^t. So that the crack of the layer will not enter the fibre but will pass around it as was shown in Fig.3. Therefore we should discuss a new model which comprises of a cylindrical fibre, a coaxial cylindrical layer and a circular notch (Fig.6). The notch tip is situated on the fibre/layer interface. Materials of the layer and the fibre are different and they can have different Young moduli E_f and E_l and tensile strength of σ_{uf}

Fig. 5. The diagram which shows how σ_{yy} is affected by t'_l .

and $\bar{\sigma}_{ul}$. The model is loaded at infinity by stresses in layer σ_l and fibre σ_f , which are proportional to Young moduli E_l and E_f .

If this model (Fig.6) was homogeneous then stress intensity factor would be calculated according to Paris and Sih (3) by the equation

$$K_I = \sigma (\pi D_0)^{1/2} f(d_f/D_0) \quad (15)$$

where σ is the nominal stress in the cross section area $\pi d_f^2/4$, factor $f(d_f/D_0)$ is a function of ratio d_f/D_0 . In composite materials the ratio d_f/D_0 has to be not less than 0,9, so $f(d_f/D_0) \approx 0,2$. But our model has two components from different materials. Therefore K_I must be affected by the ratio E_f/E_l . We can depict this effect by introducing factor α_2 in equation (15). As it has been shown earlier the factor must be more than 1, if $E_f/E_l < 1$, and less than 1, if $E_f/E_l > 1$. So that we have

$$K_I = 0,2 \alpha_2 \sigma_f (\pi D_0)^{1/2} \quad (16)$$

where σ_f is nominal stress in the fibre. It is probable that

Fig. 6. The second model of the fracture of the fibre/layer system.

$\mathcal{X}_2 \neq \mathcal{X}_1$ because the models (Fig.4 and Fig.6) are different. If we insert equations (I6) and (I3) in equation (9) and assume $t_{11} = t'_1$, $t_{12} = t'_1$, $\bar{\sigma}_{l2} = \bar{\sigma}_{ul}$, $\bar{\sigma}_f = \bar{\sigma}_{uf}$ then we shall have the equation for calculating $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\text{II}}$ at the tip of the crack for the second model (Fig.6).

$$\bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\text{II}} = 0,14 \mathcal{X}_2 (\bar{\sigma}_{ul} / E_L) E_f t_L^{1/\beta_L} (r^*)^{-1/2} (t'_1)^{-1/\beta_L} (d_f + 2t'_1)^{1/2} \quad (I7)$$

It is also necessary to remember that $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\text{I}}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\text{II}}$ are stresses which appear during fracture of the layer. In fact for both models the layer fractures at the same fracture strain $\bar{\epsilon}_{ul}$ (see equation 3). Equation (I7) shows that if $\beta_L = 3-6$ then $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\text{II}}$ will decrease with increasing of t'_1 (Fig.5). The curves of equations (I4) and (I7) intersect each other at t'_1 , which equals t_L^0

$$t_L^0 \approx 0,034 d_f \quad (I8)$$

Equation (I8) was derived by assuming that $\mathcal{X}_1 \approx \mathcal{X}_2$ (for the sake of simplicity). We can see that if $t'_1 < t_L^0$, then $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\text{II}} > \bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\text{I}}$ (Fig.5).

Now we have a diagram which shows how stress $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}$ changes with changing of the thickness of the layer. Let us analyse the diagram (Fig.5) in detail. At first it can be divided into four major areas from point of view of theoretical strength of the fibre $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t$.

Area OA.

Here $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t \leq \bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\text{I}}$ min, where $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\text{I}}$ min is minimal value of stress $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\text{I}}$. It can be calculated by inserting a value t_L^* in equation (I5). At $t'_1 \geq t_L^*$ only the first model works (Fig.4) and $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\text{I}}$ changes from point f (at $t'_1 = t_L^*$) to point l (Fig.5). The strength of the fibre $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^i$ for this area is calculated from equations

$$\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^i = \text{const} = \bar{\sigma}_{uf}^i \quad \text{at } 0 \leq t'_1 \leq t_L^* \quad (I9)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^i = (E_f / E_L) \bar{\sigma}_{ul} (t_L / t'_1)^{1/\beta_L} \quad \text{at } t'_1 \geq t_L^* \quad (20)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^i$ is the initial strength of the fibre (without layer).

These equations give a curve, which shows change of the strength of the fibre σ_{uf} as a function of the thickness of the layer (Fig.7). We can see that for the area OA, where $\sigma_{uf}^t \leq \sigma_{yy}^I$, there is only one peculiar thickness, which has been called as the critical thickness t_l^* ; the latter divides a graph in Fig.7 into two parts. For first part, where $0 \leq t_l' \leq t_l^*$, fracture of the model system is initiated by the fracture of the fibre. For second part, where $t_l' \geq t_l^*$, fracture of the model system is initiated by the fracture of the layer. Here σ_{uf} monotonly decreases with increasing of t_l' .

Area AB.

Here $\sigma_{yy}^I < \sigma_{uf}^t \leq \sigma_{yy}^s$. σ_{yy}^s is calculated by inserting t_l^0 in equations (I4) or (I7). The strength of the system is determined by equations (I9) (if $0 \leq t_l' \leq t_l^*$) and (20) (if $t_l' \geq t_l^*$). Now let us discuss a concrete example. We assume the fibre has the theoretical strength $\sigma_{uf}^t = \sigma_{uf}^{t_1^I}$ (Fig.5). We shall trace how σ_{yy} changes with increasing t_l' . If $0 \leq t_l' \leq t_l^*$ then the fracture of the system will be initiated by the fracture of the fibre, so that the strength of the system is determined by equation (I9). If $t_l^* \leq t_l' < t_l^{I'}$, then $\sigma_{yy}^I < \sigma_{uf}^t < \sigma_{yy}^{II}$. Therefore the system fractures according to the second model (Fig.6). Here σ_{yy}^{II} changes from point d (at $t_l' = t_l^*$) to point e (at $t_l' \approx t_l^{I'}$) (Fig.5). If $t_l' \geq t_l^{I'}$ then $\sigma_{uf}^{t_1^I} \leq \sigma_{yy}^I$. Here the system fractures according to the first model (Fig.4) and σ_{yy}^I changes from point m to point l. In this example fracture stress σ_{yy} changes along the curve d e m s l. If $\sigma_{uf}^{t_1^I} = \sigma_{yy}^s$ then σ_{yy} will change along the curve d e s l. For the area AB a typical graph σ_{uf} vs. t_l' is the same as the analogous graph for the area OA (Fig.7). Here also there is only one peculiar thickness of the layer - the first critical thickness t_l^* .

Area BC.

Here $\sigma_{yy}^s < \sigma_{uf}^t \leq \sigma_{yy}^{II}$. σ_{yy}^{II} is calculated by inserting t_l^* into equation (I7). If $0 \leq t_l' \leq t_l^*$ then the strength of the system will be determined by equation (I9). If $t_l' \geq t_l^*$ and $\sigma_{uf}^t \leq \sigma_{yy}^{II}$ or $\sigma_{uf}^t \leq \sigma_{yy}^I$ then it will be determined by equation (20). But in this area it is possible to meet a case, where $\sigma_{yy}^{II} < \sigma_{uf}^t > \sigma_{yy}^I$. In this case the fracture of the lay-

er does not immediately initiate fracture of the fibre. Therefore for the fracture of the fibre it is necessary to apply an additional load to the system until $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}$ will achieve $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t$. In this case the strength of the fibre is determined by the equation

$$\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t (r^*)^{1/2}}{0,14 \alpha_2 (d_f + 2t_l')^{1/2}} \quad (21)$$

Equation (21) was derived from equations (9,13,15) and it is suitable for a certain interval of values t_l' . This interval can be found by inserting $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t$ into equations (14) and (17) and by their joint solution. A typical graph $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t$ vs. t_l' for the area BC is shown in Fig.8. Let us discuss a concrete example.

We assume the fibre has the theoretical strength $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^{t_2}$ (Fig. 5). For interval $t_l' \leq t_l' \leq t_l'^2$ we have $\bar{\sigma}_{yy} \leq \bar{\sigma}_{uf}^{t_2} \leq \bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\bar{II}}$ and the system fractures according to the second model. For interval $t_l'^2 < t_l' < t_l'^3$ there is $\bar{\sigma}_{yy} < \bar{\sigma}_{uf}^{t_2} \leq \bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\bar{II}}$ and the system fractures according to the second model too. But for interval $t_l'^3 \leq t_l'$ there is $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\bar{I}} \geq \bar{\sigma}_{uf}^{t_2}$ and the system fractures according to the first model. So that for this example local fracture stress $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}$ must change along the line d_{rv} and $t_l'^2 = t_l'^{**}$, $t_l'^3 = t_l'^{***}$ (Fig.5 and Fig.8).

Fig. 7. The graph which shows how $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t$ is affected by t_l' , when $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t \leq \bar{\sigma}_{yy}$

Fig. 8. The graph which shows how $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}$ is affected by t_l' , when $\bar{\sigma}_{yys} < \bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t < \bar{\sigma}_{yy\max}^{\bar{II}}$

Area higher than point C.

Here $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t > \bar{\sigma}_{yy\max}^{\bar{II}}$. If $0 \leq t_l' \leq t_l^*$ then the strength of the fibre will be determined by equation (I9), but if $t_l' > t_l^*$, then the strength of the fibre will be determined by equation (2I), because here $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t > \bar{\sigma}_{yy\max}^{\bar{II}} > \bar{\sigma}_{yy}^{\bar{I}}$. A typical graph $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}$ vs t_l' for the area higher than point C is shown in Fig.7.

The diagram in Fig.5 shows that a situation is possible when the fracture of the layer does not immediately initiate the fracture of the fibre. The graph $\bar{\sigma}_{uf} - t_l'$ shown in Fig.8 has four specific parts and three critical thickness of the layer t_l^* , t_l^{**} and t_l^{***} . Values t_l^{**} and t_l^{***} can be calculated by equations

$$t_l^{**} = \left(\frac{E_L r^{*1/2}}{0,79 \alpha_1 \bar{\sigma}_{ul} t_l^{1/\beta_L}} \right)^{\frac{2\beta_L}{\beta_L - 2}} \quad (22)$$

$$t_l^{***} \approx d_f^{\beta_L/2} \left(1,4 \alpha_2 \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{ul}}{E_L} t_l^{1/\beta_L} r^{*-1/2} \right)^{\beta_L} \quad (23)$$

The equation for calculation $\bar{\sigma}_{yys}$ can be derived from equations (I8) and (I7) or (I4). So that we have

$$\bar{\sigma}_{yys} = 0,79 \alpha_1 \frac{E_f}{E_L} \bar{\sigma}_{ul} t_l^{1/\beta_L} r^{*-1/2} 0,034 d_f^{1/2 - 1/\beta_L} \quad (24)$$

It can be seen that an interval between t_l^{**} and t_l^{***} increases with the ratio $E_l/\bar{\sigma}_{uf}$ (through factors α_1 and α_2). In principle it is possible the third critical thickness can be missing in the area BC.

Let us come back again to Table I. We can see the systems B/(B₄C), B/(SiC) and B/(BN) are disposed in the area OA below point A in the diagram (Fig.5). But systems B/TiB₂ and B/AlB₂ are disposed in the area AB higher than point A and below point S (if $\beta_l = 4-6$). If $\beta_l = 3$ then these systems will be disposed in the area OA below point A, because in this case $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t = E_l/10 = 3800 \text{ kg/mm}^2$ is less than $\bar{\sigma}_{yymin}$. Nevertheless all five systems have a similar graph $\bar{\sigma}_f$ vs. t' which is shown in Fig. 7. But the systems B/(B₄C), B/(SiC) and B/(BN) fracture only according to the first model. The systems B/TiB₂ and B/AlB₂ fracture according to first and second models. If $t'_l < t_l^{I}$ (Fig.5) then they will fracture according to second model and if $t'_l \geq t_l^{I}$ then they will fracture according to the first model. We have met this transitive situation during calculation $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}$ due to the fracture of the layer of the critical thickness. This is shown in four last columns of Table I. When $\beta_l = 3$ then the systems B/TiB₂ and B/AlB₂ will fracture only according to the first model (Table I and Fig.7).

Table I shows for all discussed systems the fracture of the layer of any thickness t'_l ($t'_l \geq t_l^*$) immediately initiates the fracture of the fibre.

But the diagram in Fig.5 shows that in principle it is possible to meet systems where the fracture of the layer not always immediately initiates the fracture of the fibre.

Experimental verification of the theory

For experimental verification of the theory we used BorSiC fibres. Some results have been published early by (10). Diameter of the boron core was 0,1 mm. Thicknesses of layer SiC were 1,5; 3; 5 and 8,5 μ . The layers were produced by gas chemical condensation process. Temperature of the process was unchangeable for all used thickness of the layer. But duration of the process increased with the thickness of the layer. Temperature and time of the process were not so great as to reduce notice-

ably the strength of the boron fibre.

All fibres were tested on the tensile test machine "Shemadzu" with rate of deformation $0,1 \text{ sec}^{-1}$. The length gage of samples was 25 mm. The samples were prepared by standard method, which is typical for these kinds of samples.

Results of this test are shown in Table II and in Fig.9. They show that drastic decreasing of strength of the fibres will begin when thickness of the layer is more than $1,5 \mu$.

Table II. Tensile strength of the fibres B/SiC with different thickness of the layer

t_l^*, μ	$\bar{\sigma}_{u,B/SiC}$ kg/mm ²	$\bar{S}_{u,B/SiC}$ kg/mm ²	Number of samples
0	298	48,3	63
1,5	290	58,5	52
3,0	247	50,6	52
5,0	233	18,5	64
8,5	165	12,9	67

Fig.9 shows experimental and theoretical results of tensile strength of the BorSiC fibres. The calculated results are shown by curves drawn for different values of the factor β_l ($\beta_l = 4,5$ and 6). The calculated results have been produced from an equation

$$\bar{\sigma}_{u,B/SiC} = \bar{\sigma}_{u,SiC} \cdot V_{SiC} + \bar{\sigma}_{u,B} \cdot V_B$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_{u,B/SiC}$, $\bar{\sigma}_{u,SiC}$ are the tensile strength of BorSiC and SiC fibres, respectively. $\bar{\sigma}_{u,SiC}$ was calculated from equation (2) with the assumption that $\bar{\sigma}_{l2} = 200 \text{ kg/mm}^2$ if the thickness of the layer equals $0,02 \text{ mm}$ (this is equivalent to fibre diameter $0,1 \text{ mm}$). V_{SiC} is the volume fraction of SiC in BorSiC fibres ($V_{SiC} = F_{l2}$); V_B is the volume fraction of boron in BorSiC fibres. But $\bar{\sigma}_{u,B}$ is nominal tensile fracture stress in the boron component of borsic fibres. This is calculated from equation (20). We also used the following characteristic data for our calculation: $E_{SiC} = 47000 \text{ kg/mm}^2$; $E_B = 38000 \text{ kg/mm}^2$ and the

Fig. 9. Experimental results of tensile testing of BorSiC fibres with different thicknesses of the SiC layer. The curves were theoretically calculated.

tensile strength of boron fibres (without SiC layer), which equaled 298 kg/mm^2 (see Tables I and II). Critical thicknesses of the SiC layer t'_L^* , calculated from equation (7), are equal to 3,88; 2,15; 1,18 and $0,65 \mu\text{m}$ for $\beta_L = 3; 4; 5$ and 6 respectively.

We can see that experimental and theoretical data for $\beta_L = 4-5$ coincide quite well. These values of β_L were more typical for SiC fibres. Nevertheless there is quite a big discrepancy between experimental and theoretical data at thickness $8,5 \mu\text{m}$. Further study has shown that the tensile strength of the boron fibres in itself drastically decreased due to too long period of the deposition process of the SiC layer with the thickness of $8,5 \mu\text{m}$. Annealed boron fibres had the ultimate tensile strength: $\bar{\sigma}_{u, B} = 229 \text{ kg/mm}^2$. This and probably residual stresses in the components are reasons of the discrepancy. The theoretical critical thickness of the layer t'_L^* disposes between points B (for $\beta_L = 4$) and C (for $\beta_L = 5$) (see Fig.9). It is more probable that t'_L^* equals $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$.

The general conclusion from these experimental data is that our theoretical treatment is confirmed by the experimental data, received from tests of B/SiC fibres.

Method of assessment of K_{IC} of brittle fibres

Archangelskaya I.N. and Mileiko S.T. (II) have obtained an equation which allows us to calculate K_{IC} of fibre composite materials, if we know K_{IC} of matrix and fibres. At the moment there is no way of determining K_{IC} of fibres.

Previous sections of this paper give an opportunity to develop a theoretical method of assessment of K_{IC} of brittle fibres. Let us come back to model I (Fig.4), which represents a brittle fibre and a brittle layer. Assumptions of model I can be seen in section 2 of this paper. A crack in the layer is in fact a notch on the fibre. We assume the following. 1) The model under consideration has a thickness of the layer, which equals the first critical thickness t_l^* . 2) $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}$ equals $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t = E_f/10$. This means that an appearance of the crack in the layer of the critical thickness immediately initiates a fracture of the fibre, if $\bar{\sigma}_{yy} = \bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t$. In this case nominal tensile stress in the fibre must be equal to the tensile strength of the fibre, which has no layer, because t_l^* is not more than t_l^* (see Fig.7).

This situation can be met in real systems, which are analogous to the systems like B/TiB₂ and B/AlB₂, if t_l^* of them equals 0,0566 μ at $\beta_l = 3,94$ or 3,56 respectively. The situation can be expressed by an equation, which is analogous to equation (I2); but we have to insert in equation (I2) $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t$ instead of $\bar{\sigma}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t$ instead of $\bar{\sigma}_{yy}$. So that we have

$$\bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t = 0,79 \alpha_1 \bar{\sigma}_{uf} (t^*/r^*)^{1/2} \quad (25)$$

As we have shown the stress intensity factor of model I is expressed by equation (II). This equation can be used for the above case in the following way. We assume $K_I = K_{IC}$, if $\bar{\sigma} = \bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t$ and $t_l^* = a$. So that the following joint treatment of equations (25) and (II) will give us equation

$$K_{IC} \cong 2,5 \bar{\sigma}_{uf}^t r^*{}^{1/2} \quad (26)$$

We can transform equation (26) into another, if we insert $E_f/10$ instead of σ_{uf}^t

$$K_{IC} \cong 0,25 E_f r^* \text{ }^{1/2} \quad (27)$$

Equation (27) shows that only Young modulus of the fibre has a strong effect on the critical stress intensity factor of the fibre. Equation (27) also shows that K_{IC} of the brittle fibres is not affected by its structure.

In Table III are shown calculated values of K_{IC} for the majority of well-known high-strength brittle fibres.

For this calculation we used $r^* = \text{const} = 3 \cdot 10^{-7}$ mm. In reality the lattice dimension is slightly different for different materials of the fibres. But this is not so important for our calculations because the latter must be considered for the present as approximate. It is interesting to note as Kelly (6) has shown the available data of K_{IC} for bulk alumina and reactor graphite equals 13-14 and 1,4-4,3 respectively.

Table III. Calculated values of K_{IC} of some high-strength brittle fibres

Fibre	E_f , kg/mm ²	K_{IC} , kg/mm ^{3/2}
Al ₂ O ₃	47000	6,43
Carbon, type I	39000	5,34
Carbon, type II	24000	3,29
BN	9000	1,23
B	38000	5,20
SiC	47000	6,43
TiB ₂	51000	6,98
B ₄ C	47000	6,43

Conclusion

It has been shown that the brittle layer in the fibre composite material reduces the ultimate tensile strength of latter, if the thickness of the layer is more than the critical one. Derived equation for calculation of the critical thickness of the layer shows that it is proportional to diameter of the fibre

and is affected by the ultimate tensile strength and Young's moduli of the fibre and the layer. It has been derived equations which show the effect of the thickness of the layer on the ultimate tensile strength of the layer/fibre system. Experimental results which have been done with borsic fibres fitted to theoretical results well. For example, the critical thickness of the layer for this fibres equals $1,0-1,5 \mu$. This theory helped to develop a method for theoretical calculation the critical stress intensity factor K_{IC} for the brittle fibres. According to this method K_{IC} is proportional to Young moduli of the fibre.

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